

‘Sort by relevance’ project: Survey structure

About this document

This is a supporting output from the project “Sort by relevance’: Exploring assumptions about algorithm-mediated academic literature searches’. The project was undertaken during 2022 and funded by the Society for Research in Higher Education (SRHE).

The project was focused upon the use of ranking algorithms in academic literature searches (such as Google Scholar), and sought to explore the assumptions users hold about how the algorithms work, and the implications for practice.

This document contains the questions included in the online survey undertaken by the project. For further information, the project report will be available to download from the SRHE website at: <https://srhe.ac.uk/research/completed-award-reports/> .

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Survey questions

Q1 Please indicate whether you agree with the terms of the study and give your consent to participate in the survey:

- I agree - proceed to survey questions
 I do not agree and do not wish to take part in the survey

Q2 This study is focused on online databases used to search for academic literature. Examples of such databases include Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science - but there are many more online databases which are available.

In particular, this study is looking at how algorithms are used to rank search results in these online databases according to 'relevance', and what is meant by 'relevance' on different platforms.

When you need to find academic literature, how often do you carry out searches using the following databases? Note that in addition to the databases listed below, you can also add up to three other sources you use if they are not listed here already.

	I use this for every literature search	I often use this for literature searches	I rarely use this but have at least once	I am aware of this database, but have never used it	I am not aware of it and have never used it
Academia.edu					
Aminer					
Arxiv					
Dimensions.ai					
Google Scholar					
JSTOR					
Lens.org					
Pubmed					
ResearchGate					
Science Direct					
Scopus					
Semantic Scholar					
University library search portal					

Web of Science					
Zenodo					

Q3 If you know the name of your library search portal, please add it below.

Q4 How important do you consider the following factors to be when deciding how useful an article is likely to be?

Note that in addition to the criteria listed below, you can also add and rate up to three additional types of information.

	Very important (a high priority)	Important	Neither important nor unimportant	Unimportant	Very unimportant (not relevant at all)
Who the author is					
The journal the paper was published in					
How many citations the paper has received					
The paper being available in English					
How recently the paper was published					
The paper matches the exact keywords used for the search					
The paper matches the subject area the search keywords relate to					

Q5 When you are searching for academic literature, what are the databases you would be most likely to use? Please write the names of up to three databases in the text boxes below (one per box).

Database 1: _____

Database 2: _____

Database 3: _____

Q6 Thinking about your use of [Database 1], please describe briefly why you use this platform, and the benefits of using it:

Q7 Please briefly describe here any constraints or disadvantages of using [Database 1].

Q8 Thinking about the last time you used [Database 1] for a literature search, how do you think the platform defines the order in which search results are ranked?

Q9 Thinking about your use of [Database 2], please describe briefly why you use this platform, and the benefits of using it:

Q10 Please briefly describe here any constraints or disadvantages of using [Database 2].

Q11 Thinking about the last time you used [Database 2] for a literature search, how do you think the platform defines the order in which search results are ranked?

Q12 Thinking about your use of [Database 3], please describe briefly why you use this platform, and the benefits of using it:

Q13 Please briefly describe here any constraints or disadvantages of using [Database 3].

Q14 Thinking about the last time you used [Database 3] for a literature search, how do you think the platform defines the order in which search results are ranked?

Q15 The following questions ask about demographic information. This is intended to allow us to look for any patterns in the data. The questions are optional; if you do not wish to answer a particular question, please skip and move on to the next one.

Q15-1 What is the name of the department, unit or service you are based in?

Q15-2 What is your main research topic/interest?

Q15-3 Which country are you based in?

Q15-4 Which university (or universities) are you currently affiliated with?

Q15-5 What is your current job title?

Q16 Which discipline(s) does your academic work sit within?

- Arts and Humanities
- Biomedical sciences
- Engineering and technological sciences
- Natural sciences
- Social sciences

Q17 After the survey has concluded, we plan to hold a number of interviews to discuss the assumptions of ranking by relevance in more detail. If you would be willing to be contacted about potentially taking part in an online interview, please add your email address here:

Q18 If there is anything which you would like to add about relevance ranking algorithms in literature searches, please add a comment here:

Q19 How did you find out about this survey?

Q20 If you would like to receive a summary of the findings from the project when it is completed, please add your email address here:
